

Evaluation of Pre Menstrual Syndrome among Female Students Age Group (18-25) Years

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Abstract:- Premenstrual syndrome refers to changes in mood and emotion, physical health, and behavior that develop between ovulation and the onset of Menstruation. Premenstrual Syndrome is a psychosomatic disorder. It last until a few days after the Menstruation begins. It is estimated one-fourth population of Women has experienced some form of premenstrual syndrome. The study is designed as a questionnaire and is distributed to female students. This study was conducted to assess the Pre Menstrual syndrome among female students age group (18 - 25) years at Sree Ramakrishna Medical College of Naturopathy and Yogic Sciences and Hospital, Kulasekharam, Tamil Nadu, India. Verbal consent was taken from the female students by explaining the purpose of the study. The total number of study respondents was 30. The questionnaire contains 30 questions. The parameters of the questionnaire included physical and mental changes during pre-menstrual syndrome.

In this study, awareness of the pre-menstrual syndrome and regular menstruation is satisfactory. But, the mental changes, gastrointestinal discomfort, and urogenital symptoms are more. Therefore, female students need more awareness about mental, gastrointestinal, and urogenital health.

Keywords:- *gastrointestinal discomfort, pain, mental changes, breast tenderness, pre menstrual syndrome.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Menstruation is a normal phenomenon that is an important indicator of women's health. Premenstrual syndrome is a psychosomatic disorder. It is one of the most common disorders in women of reproductive age. The exact cause of the disease is unknown. There will be natural fluctuation in hormone levels mainly estrogen and progesterone. Estrogen and Progesterone decrease slowly after ovulation. This may play a major role in development of the premenstrual syndrome. It occurs just before menstruation. There is a cyclic appearance of a large number of symptoms during the last 7 to 10 days of the Menstrual cycle. Regularly occurs during the luteal phase of each ovulatory menstrual cycle. Symptoms may differ, and

sometimes, it may affect the lifestyle of the women. Its estimated one-fourth population of women has experienced some form of premenstrual syndrome. Symptoms usually reduce during or at the onset of menstruation.

II. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The exact cause of the syndrome is unknown, but, some of the factors that may cause this condition include fluctuation of hormones, mainly estrogen and progesterone, genetic cause, serotonin deficiency, calcium, and magnesium deficiency. It is related to neuroendocrine events occurring within the anterior pituitary gland. The most common symptoms are irritability, anxiety, agitation, anger, Insomnia, lethargy, depression, and severe fatigue, breast tenderness, backache, Lack of concentration. The other symptoms such as headache, constipation, nausea, vomiting, changes in appetite, acne, skin disorders, and mood disorders. Teenagers often present with moderate to severe symptoms. Some lifestyle factors, such as smoking, junk food, and lack of physical activity can cause the premenstrual syndrome.

III. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study is designed as a questionnaire and is distributed to the female students' age group (18 - 25) years at Sree Ramakrishna Medical College of Naturopathy and Yogic Sciences and Hospital, Kulasekharam, Tamil Nadu, India. Verbal consent was taken from the female students by explaining the purpose of the study. The total number of study respondents was 30. The questionnaire contains 30 questions. The parameters of the questionnaire included pain, habit, gastrointestinal, urogenital discomfort and mental changes during premenstrual syndrome. Those females who did not cooperate and were non-willing participants were excluded from the study.

IV. RESULT

The sociodemographic character showed that the respondents were between the age group of (18 - 25) years. The total number of female students is n=30. Table 1 shows, mental changes during premenstrual syndrome, the mood changes before menstruation 24(80%), while, 6(20%) do not have mood changes before menstruation. Lack of concentration 14(46.66%) and do not have lack of concentration 16(53.33%). Lack of interest in any activities before menstruation 19(63.33%), and do not have this

symptom 11(36.66%). Overthinking before the onset of menstruation 17(56.66%), and do not have to overthink 13(43.33%). Sound sleep before the onset of menstruation 14(46.66%), and do not have sound sleep 16(53.33%). The symptoms of irritability, anger, anxious before premenstrual syndrome 27(90%), and do not have this symptom 3(10%). Hallucination before the onset of menstruation 4(13.33%), do not have hallucination 26(86.66%), fear and frustration before menstruation 2(6.66%), while, 28(93.33%) do not have fear and frustration before menstruation.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Mood changes before menstruation	24(80%)	6(20%)
2	Lack of concentration	14(46.66%)	16(53.33%)
3	Lack of Interest	19(63.33%)	11(36.66%)
4	Over thinking	17(56.66%)	13(43.33%)
5	Sound sleep	14(46.66%)	16(53.33%)
6	Irritability, Anger, Anxious	27(90%)	3(10%)
7	Hallucination	4(13.33%)	26(86.66%)
8	Fear Symptoms	2(6.66%)	28(93.33%)
9	Awareness about PMS	26(86.66%)	4(13.33%)
10	Restlessness Symptoms	21(70%)	9(30%)

Table 1: Mental Changes during Pre Menstrual Syndrome

Awareness about pre menstruation syndrome 26(86.66%), and do not have awareness 4(13.33%), restlessness before the onset of menstruation 21(70%), and 9(30%) do not have restlessness.

Table 2 shows, the symptom of breast tenderness before the onset of menstruation 14(46.66%), and 16(53.33%) do not have the symptom of breast tenderness. Symptoms of Joint Pain 15(50%), and 15(50%) do not have the Symptom of joint pain.

SNO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Symptom of breast tenderness	14(46.66%)	16(53.33%)
2	Joint Pain	15(50%)	15(50%)
3	Back Pain	23(76.66%)	7(23.33%)
4	Migraine	4(13.33%)	26(86.66%)

Table 2: Pain Symptoms during Pre Menstrual Syndrome

The symptom of back pain is 23(76.66%), and do not have the symptom of back pain 7(23.33%). The symptom of

migraine before the onset of menstruation 4(13.33%), and 26(86.66%) do not have the symptom of migraine.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Food craving symptom	14(46.66%)	16(53.33%)
2	Medication	Nil	30(100%)
3	Tea, Coffee	14(46.66%)	16(53.33%)

Table 3: Habits during Pre Menstrual syndrome

Table 3 shows, the symptom of food craving before the onset of menstruation 14(46.66%), while, 16(53.33%) do not have this symptom. No one is taking medication before

the onset of menstruation 30(100%), The habit of tea, and coffee 14(46.66%), and 16(53.33%) do not have the habit.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Regular Periods	30(100%)	Nil
2	White discharge	22(73.33%)	8(26.66%)

Table 4: Urogenital Symptoms during Pre Menstrual Syndrome

Table 4 shows, the female students those having regular menstruation 30(100%), and The symptom of white discharge before the onset of menstruation 22(73.33%), and 8(26.66%) do not have white discharge before the onset of menstruation.

Table 5 shows, abdomen bloating before the onset of menstruation 13(43.33%), and 17(56.66%) do not have abdomen bloating before the onset of menstruation. The heaviness of the abdomen before menstruation is 12(40%), while 18(60%) do not have the heaviness of the abdomen

before menstruation. 12(40%) have the symptom of constipation before the onset of menstruation, and 18(60%)

do not have the symptom of constipation before the onset of menstruation.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Abdomen Bloating	13(43.33%)	17(56.66%)
2	Abdomen heaviness	12(40%)	18(60%)
3	Constipation	12(40%)	18(60%)
4	Vomiting	7(23.33%)	23(76.66%)
5	Indigestion	8(26.66%)	22(73.33%)
6	Diarrhoea	13(43.33%)	17(56.66%)
7	Regurgitation	2(6.66%)	28(93.33%)

Table 5: gastro intestinal discomfort during Pre Menstrual Syndrome

Vomiting symptoms before the onset of menstruation 7(23.33%), while 23(76.66%), do not have vomiting symptoms before the onset of menstruation. Indigestion before menstruation 8(26.66%), and 22(73.33%), do not have indigestion. Diarrhoea before the onset of menstruation

13(43.33%), while 17(56.66%), do not have diarrhoea. Regurgitation before the onset of menstruation 2(6.66%), and 28(93.33%), do not have regurgitation before the onset of menstruation.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Increased body temperature	20(66.66%)	10(33.33%)
2	Acne	25(83.33%)	5(16.66%)
3	Shivering	7(23.33%)	23(76.66%)
4	Discomfort	25(83.33%)	5(16.66%)

Table 6: Other symptoms during Pre Menstrual Syndrome

The other symptoms such as increased body temperature before the onset of menstruation 20(66.66%), and 10(33.33%) do not have increased body temperature before the onset of menstruation. Acne appears before the onset of menstruation 25(83.33%), while 5(16.66%), do not have acne before the onset of menstruation. Shiver before the onset of menstruation 7(23.33%), and 23(76.66%) do not shiver before the onset of menstruation. Discomfort occurs before the onset of menstruation 25(83.33%), while 5(16.66%), do not have discomfort before the onset of menstruation.

menstruation 30(100%), majority of female students 22(73.33%) have the symptom of white discharge before the onset of menstruation. Fewer female students have the symptom of abdomen bloating 13(43.33%), and constipation symptoms 12(40%) before the onset of menstruation 13(43.33%). The majority of female students have the symptom of increased body temperature 20(66.66%), acne 25(83.33%), and discomfort 25(83.33%) before the onset of menstruation.

V. DISCUSSION

Mood changes before menstruation 24(80%), majority of female students have mood changes, lack of concentration 14(46.66%), lack of Interest before menstruation 19(63.33%). Overthinking before the onset of menstruation 17(56.66%). The symptoms of anger and anxiety before mensuration 27(90%). Sound sleep before the onset of menstruation 14(46.66%). Awareness about pre-menstruation syndrome 26(86.66%), the majority of female students aware of the pre-menstruation syndrome. Restlessness before the onset of menstruation 21(70%), most of the female students have restlessness before the onset of menstruation. Fewer female students have the symptom of breast tenderness before the onset of menstruation 14(46.66%). About 50% Of the female students have the symptoms of joint pain. The majority of female students have the symptoms of back pain 23(76.66%). The symptom of food craving before the onset of menstruation 14(46.66%), Fewer female students have the symptom of food craving. No one is taking medication before the onset of menstruation 30(100%), The habit of drinking tea or coffee 14(46.66%), and most of the female students have the habit of drinking tea or coffee. All are having regular

VI. CONCLUSION

This study shows that the awareness of the premenstrual syndrome and regular menstruation is satisfactory. Mental changes, gastrointestinal discomfort, and urogenital symptoms are more. Therefore, female students need more awareness about mental, gastrointestinal, and urogenital health.

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